

AWARENESS ABOUT NEW EDUCATION POLICY IN TEACHERS OF U.T. OF DADRA AND NAGAR HAVELI

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ABSTRACT

After 34 years, the Indian Government has launched new education policy with remarkable changes in the year 2020. Education department and policy makers perform their role in Formulation and implementation of new policy but there are teachers who implement those recommendations and changes at school level and student level. Hence, it is very important to facilitate teachers with various resources and to train teachers for new approaches of the policy. So, the researchers found it important to focus on awareness about new education policy in teachers

of U.T. of Dadra and Nagar Haveli. In the present research, researchers tried to check awareness in teachers about NEP 2020. And tried to know teachers' knowledge regarding NEP 2020. The major findings of the research were as under:

- *There is a scope to increase awareness about NEP 2020 amongst the teachers.*
- *There is no any remarkable difference in the awareness NEP 2020 in teachers with respect to their gender, locality of the schools and teaching experience.*

NEP 2020 is a National Educational Policy proposed by the Government with remarkable changes. All teachers must be aware of the NEP 2020 regarding school education system. Teachers can understand the challenges in proper implementation of NEP 2020 practically and be prepared with possible solutions for the same. Teachers with proper understanding of NEP 2020 can guide students properly for their career. It is in the hands of teachers to apply it practically and to make it effective, fruitful and successful. Hence, it is very important to facilitate teachers with various resources and to train teachers for new approaches of the policy.

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Key Words: Awareness, New Education Policy (NEP), Teachers.

Introduction

Education plays a vital role in building nation, education decides the future of nation, destiny of its people. India was well known name in the world in reference to the education system since ancient time. The gurukul system of imparting education is very well known worldwide. The education system in India has changed gradually after independence. India has gone through two major education policies after independence.

1. National Policy on Education 1968 (NPE-1968)

2. National policy on Education 1986 (NPE-1986)

3. National Education policy 2020 (NEP-2020)

NEP 2020 is a National Educational Policy proposed by the Government of India in the year 2020. The year 2020 will be memorable not only for the impacts of COVID -19 but also for the remarkable changes proposed in the education policy NEP 2020. Below are the few highlighting features of NEP 2020 regarding school education system.

- The 10+2 structure of school curriculum will now be replaced by 5+3+3+4 curricular structure. Which is corresponding to ages 3 to 8, 8 to 11, 11 to 14 and 14 to 18 years respectively.
- As per NEP 2020, Board exams of std. 10th and std. 12th will be taken twice a year.
- As per NEP 2020, PARAKH will be new set up as a national assessment center for setting norms, standards and guidelines for students' assessment and evaluation for all recognized school boards.
- NEP 2020 emphasizes on vocational skill-based training from class 6th onwards.
- As per NEP 2020, students from class 9th are allowed to choose their subject combinations.

Objectives

1. To check the awareness amongst teachers about national education policy 2020.
2. To know the difference of awareness related to national education policy 2020 with respect to gender, locality of school and experience of teachers.

Methodology

The researchers applied descriptive survey method out of different methods of conducting research to fulfill objectives of the present study.

Sample

The sample of study comprised of 50 teachers from various schools of U.T. of Dadra and Nagar Haveli. The teachers were selected as a sample through random sampling technique. For the random selection of teachers, lottery method was applied by the researchers. The selection of sample is shown in the table: 1.

Table: 1

Sr. No.	Name of the School	Location of the School	No. of male teachers	No. of female teachers	Total No. of teachers	Experience			
1	Govt. High School, Silvassa	Urban	04	06	10	Below 5 yrs.	02		
						5 – 10 yrs.	04		
						Above 10 yrs.	04		
2	Prabhat Scholars Academy, Silvassa		Urban	02	07	09	Below 5 yrs.	04	
							5 – 10 yrs.	05	
							Above 10 yrs.	00	
3	Lions English School, Silvassa			Urban	06	05	11	Below 5 yrs.	02
								5 – 10 yrs.	02
								Above 10 yrs.	07

4	Govt. High School, Surangi	Rural	06	06	12	Below 5 yrs.	03
						5 – 10 yrs.	01
						Above 10 yrs.	08
5	Smt. M.G.Lunavat English School, Dadra.	Rural	01	09	10	Below 5 yrs.	07
						5 – 10 yrs.	01
						Above 10 yrs.	02
6	Gyanmata English High school, Khanvel	Rural	06	02	08	Below 5 yrs.	04
						5 – 10 yrs.	03
						Above 10 yrs.	01
Total			25	35	60	-	60

Tools

For the present study self-constructed questionnaire was used by the researchers to collect the data. The details of the inventory.

- Questionnaire was consisting of eight questions to check the knowledge of teachers regarding national education policy 2020.

Analysis and interpretation of the Data

➤ Analysis and interpretation of the Data collected through questionnaire with respect to gender.

Table: 2

Gender	Total Number (N)	Marks	Mean
Male	25	100	4.0
Female	35	188	5.3

Table: 3

Sr. No.	Question	No. of Correct response	
		Male (out of 25)	Female (out of 35)
1	What is the full form of NEP?	19	32
2	NEP 2020 is the _____ Education Policy of Government of India?	04	17
3	Who was the chairman of NEP 2020?	23	34
4	As per NEP 2020 age group 3 to 8 is ___ stage of schooling?	04	07
5	As per NEP 2020 what is the minimum age to get admission in 1 st standard?	03	07
6	Current 10+2 system to be replaced by which new curricular structure as per NEP?	17	34
7	According to NEP 2020 children may be taught in mother tongue/regional language up to which grade?	19	33
8	As per NEP 2020 learning should be _____.	11	24
Total		100	188

The data shown in table no. 2 reveals that total marks secured by male and female are 100 and 188 respectively. The mean values of male and female scores are 4.0 and 5.3 respectively.

By the analysis of data, it is concluded that marks obtained by females are slightly higher than the marks of males. Data shows that mean value of female is greater than male. But the difference of mean values is not remarkable.

- Analysis and interpretation of the Data collected through questionnaire with respect to location of the school.

Table: 4

Area	Total Number (N)	Marks	Mean
Rural	30	131	4.4
Urban	30	157	5.2

Table: 5

Sr. No.	Question	No. of Correct response	
		Rural (out of 30)	Urban (out of 30)
1	What is the full form of NEP?	23	28
2	NEP 2020 is the _____ Education Policy of Government of India?	10	11
3	Who was the chairman of NEP 2020?	24	33
4	As per NEP 2020 age group 3 to 8 is ____ stage of schooling?	10	01
5	As per NEP 2020 what is the minimum age to get admission in 1 st standard?	04	06
6	Current 10+2 system to be replaced by which new curricular structure as per NEP?	23	28
7	According to NEP 2020 children may be taught in mother tongue/regional language up to which grade?	24	28
8	As per NEP 2020 learning should be _____.	13	22
Total		131	157

The data shown in table no. 4 reveals that total marks secured by teachers of rural and urban schools are 131 and 157 respectively. The mean values of teachers of rural and urban schools are 4.4 and 5.2 respectively. By the analysis of data, it is concluded that marks obtained by the teachers in urban schools are slightly higher than the marks of teachers in rural school. Data shows that mean value of the teachers in urban schools is greater than the teachers in rural school. But the difference of mean values is not remarkable.

- Analysis and interpretation of the Data collected through questionnaire with respect to experience of teachers.

Table: 6

Experience	Total Number (N)	Marks	Mean
Below 5 yrs.	22	126	5.7
5-10 yrs.	16	70	4.3
Above 10 yrs.	22	92	4.1

Table: 7

Sr. No.	Question	No. ofCorrect response		
		Below 5 yrs. (out of 22)	5-10 yrs. (out of 16)	Above 10 yrs. (out of 22)
1	What is the full form of NEP?	22	14	15
2	NEP 2020 is the _____ Education Policy of Government of India?	15	01	05
3	Who was the chairman of NEP 2020?	20	15	22
4	As per NEP 2020 age group 3 to 8 is _____ stage of schooling?	04	03	04
5	As per NEP 2020 what is the minimum age to get admission in 1 st standard?	04	03	03
6	Current 10+2 system to be replaced by which new curricular structure as per NEP?	20	14	17
7	According to NEP 2020 children may be taught in mother tongue/regional language up to which grade?	20	14	18
8	As per NEP 2020 learning should be _____.	21	06	08
Total		126	70	92

The data shown in table no. 6 reveals that total marks secured by teachers having experience of below 5 yrs., between 5 to 10 yrs. and above 10 yrs. are 126, 70 and 92 respectively. The mean values of teachers having experience of below 5 yrs., between 5 to 10 yrs. and above 10 yrs. are 5.7, 4.3 and 4.1 respectively.

By the analysis of data, it is concluded that marks obtained by the teachers having experience of below 5 yrs. is slightly greater than the marks of teachers having experience of 5 to 10 yrs. and teachers having experience of above 10 yrs. Data shows that mean value of the teachers having experience of below 5 yrs. is slightly greater than the marks of teachers having experience of 5 to 10 yrs. The difference of mean values of teachers having experience of below 5 yrs., between 5 to 10 yrs. and above 10 yrs. is not remarkable.

Major Findings

- Data denotes that the teachers are having some information about NEP 2020 as overall correct response given by them is about around fifty percent.
- There is no remarkable difference between the scores of male and female teachers. So, it can be concluded that the male and female teachers have equal awareness about NEP 2020.
- No remarkable difference is found between the scores of the teachers in schools of urban and rural area. So, the teachers in the urban and rural area have same level of awareness about NEP 2020.
- It is found that the teachers having experience below five years have scored more marks than other teachers having experience of five to ten years and more than ten years. The teachers with less experience are comparatively more aware about NEP 2020.

Suggestions

- Teachers should be well explained and well-trained regarding NEP 2020, in order to increase the awareness about NEP 2020 and for proper implementation of NEP 2020.

- Workshops, seminar and conferences and discussions should be arranged by schools to provide platform for the brainstorming regarding features of NEP 2020.
- Experienced teachers should be involved effectively for the exposure to understand NEP 2020.

Conclusion

NEP 2020 is a National Educational Policy proposed by the Government of India in the year 2020. Remarkable changes proposed in the education policy NEP 2020. All teachers must be aware of the NEP 2020 regarding school education system. Teachers should be able to understand the challenges they may find in order to implement NEP 2020 and be prepared with possible solutions for the same. Teachers with proper understanding of NEP 2020 can guide students properly for their career. Policy makers or Education department of Government frame education policies, provide guidance and facilitate schools to implement new policies but it is in the hands of teachers to apply it practically and to make it effective, fruitful and successful. Hence, it is very important to facilitate teachers with various resources and to train teachers for new approaches of the policy.

References:

- Kumar. K. (2005). Quality of Education at the beginning of the 21st Century: Lessons from India. *Indian Educational Review*. 40(1).3.28.
- Draft National Education Policy 2019. <https://innovate.mygov.in/wp-content/2019/06/mygov15596510111.pdf>
- Nandini, ed. (29 July 2020). “New Education Policy 2020 Highlights: School and higher education to see major changes” *Hindustan Times*. Retrieved 30 July 2020.
 - Jebaraj, Priscilla (2 August 2020). “The Hindu Explains | What has the National Education Policy 2020 proposed?” *The Hindu*. ISSN 0971-751X. Retrieved 2 August 2020. <https://www.ruralindiaonline.org/>
 - <https://www.education.gov.in>